

Assessment of Pre-Retirement Anxiety on Job Performance among Academic Staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper assessed pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Three (3) objectives and research questions each guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. The population of this study consists of all academic staff in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. A sample size of two hundred and fourteen (214) academic staff was selected at random from a total of four hundred and eighty (480) respondents using multi-stage sampling technique. Academic staff questionnaire (ACSQ) was used as instrument for data collection in this study. Instrument was vetted and reliability co-efficient of 0.89 was obtained. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean and standard deviation respectively was used for data analysis. The findings of this study revealed that pre - retirement anxiety has strong effect on job performance of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Also, the causes of anxiety prior to retirement of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria are many only that fear of regular income as wages or allowances as well as inability to adjust to new social status in the society are evidently topping the list. The study recommended that staff due for retirement should be well guided and supported to accept their destiny in good fate but not as something that would make them to lack focus and thus produced poor results in what they are teaching. Finally, the government should strengthen and supervise the activities of various Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs) in the Country to allay the fear of staff that their remittances while still working will continue to come regularly even in retirement.

Keywords: Academic Staff (teachers), Effects, Job Performance, Pre - Retirement.

Introduction

Human existence is full of mystery of one form or the other. In essence, there exist a time for the unemployed to scout for work, resumed and later on, leave the system on accounts of retirement, death or dismissal. In all these, one of the phases of life that is most honourable is retirement, which could be voluntary, coerced or early in nature. Judging from this, retirement is considered an inevitable reality in every organized profession be it public service or private sector. Although, most transitions in life are foreseeable and thus, allowed for a period of preparation to be set in motion, for those not anticipated, it comes with little or no forward planning by those concerned. Regardless of the preceding factors, transitional periods are often accompanied by a re-evaluation of one's life, including a shift in self - identity and re - direction of energies for the time in order not to come as a shock (Chow, 2001). For whatsoever, there is the issue of pre - retirement anxiety on the part of many including academic staff of tertiary institutions in the Country.

The inability of workers to perceive retirement positively and make adequate plans for it does provoke anxiety. So also, the absence of meeting the estimated or calculated target plans that are usually set in place before retirement also trigger such an anxiety. Many at times, the deteriorating condition of employee been retired is presumed to be one of the factors that cause pre - retirement anxiety (Ukaegbu, 2023). However, this may change depending on many other factors such as individual differences, entitlement by the organization and environment factors. In developed countries retirement is usually guided, controlled and maintained at the right time such that workers may pass through it successfully unlike what is observed in developing countries like Nigeria (Ogunyemi and Oderinde, 2018). The predicaments of retirees in Nigeria has not only

demoralized the psyche of workers still in service, but has also affected how they performed their work prior to the time of retirement. Invariably, the anxiety associated with occupational losses describes an individual's concern about life after work. Hence the worry relating to retirement incorporates pre-retirement anxiety of one sort or another. It is worrisome to note that most workers as observed have no plans at all for retirement and by the time they realize it. It is already too late hence the need to undertake a study of this nature.

Job performance by teachers is highly inevitable in any educational institution. It could however be determined by the extent of how motivated they are. In other words, staff motivation and performance are fundamental variables notwithstanding as it affects or otherwise of an educational institution. Academic staff job performance refers to how your workers behave in the work place and how well they do the job assigned to them (Ashley in Udu, Ogbaga and Ibenwo, 2022). He also posits that performance includes work effectiveness, quality and efficiency at work. It is a standard for employee behaviour at work. In this context, academic staff are rated on how well they do their jobs compared with a set of standards determined by the employer (Maria, 2017). This is most adjudged via annual performance evaluation and review (APER) form expected to be filled by teaching and non-teaching staff alike. Few of the components of performance include punctuality, quality of work done and employee commitment.

According to numerous researches, working in any type of educational institution is the most demanding occupation when compared to other careers. This is especially with poor working conditions in schools which has necessitated a high level of physical, intellectual, and emotional imbalance for the teachers involved. However, there are a variety of emotional and knowledgeable indicators of task anxiety that could bother teachers individually, negatively impacting their ability to teach the youngsters (Asaloei, Wolomasi and Werang, 2020). As academics, they are saddled to teach, research, and carry out other academic services in the colleges. Their roles of course as academic staff in the development of higher institutions cannot be underestimated because they are the implementers of instruction in these educational institutions (Ogunode, Jegede and Abubakar, 2020). The job performed however is critical to the realization of teacher education objectives. To buttress further on this point, academic staff job performance connotes assigned responsibilities and functions given to actualize the aims and objectives of the institutions and the decree of its execution or accomplishment. Job performance is therefore the result of individual or group work that shows the level of achievement of job qualifications in organizations that aim to meet organizational goals (Al- Omari and Okasheh, 2017).

Retirement marks a major life change for many people. This is because income, status, responsibilities, activities and social relationship associated with the work environment suddenly change due to what may be referred to as pre-retirement anxiety of the would-be-retired officer (Adisa, 2003). It is important to note that retirement is different for everyone depending on the type and reason for disengagement. According to Musa (2004), retirement to many, is the end of a happy life. Other sees it as the end of being useful in any way. The announcement of retirement grips many with agony and pain. Musa stated further that, some see retirement as a curse rather than a blessing because it is like the curtain of useful life has been drawn to a close. But in actual sense, Abdullah (2004) observed that a retiree is supposed to be happy, rejoicing and thanking God for the long life he has enjoyed as an active participant in national development and he still has time to enjoy the third phase of life which is the retirement period.

Pre-retirement on the other hand, is the period right before retirement when an employee's duties and possibilities are diminishing (Szinovacs in Wilcox and Dimkpa, 2023). Pre - retirement anxiety is an antecedent disturbance that often sets in a year or two before one actually leaves the job; it further involves anxieties and worries about the individual's future as a result of the termination of active working life (Nefer, 2015). In support of this, Wilcox and Dimkpa (2023) stated that recent statistical evidence supports the fact that pre-retirement anxiety has become a huge problem in Nigeria. For example, it was found that (68.1%) of retiring civil servants in Edo State of Nigeria experienced high retirement anxiety (Oghogho and Nwankwo, 2022). Judging from the current economic crisis in the Country, it is becoming increasingly difficult for the average Nigerian worker, particularly the future retiree, to make ends meet, because most of them still have families and wards who are primarily dependent on them. Similarly, Young and Zhou (2017) were of the view that the anxiety envisaged by civil servants prior to their retirement may be associated with their unpreparedness, coupled with the adverse psychological and socio - economic dispositions that plaque civil servants as a result of functional discrimination in their finances and source of livelihood; and decline in their social status. Other researchers have also identified certain difficulties faced by retirees as a pointer to investigating this study, which includes financial challenges, loneliness, lack of comfortable accommodation, high blood pressure, loss of self-esteem, lower status, among others (Hansson, Buratti, Johansson and Berg, 2019).

Every worker has his/her stipulated time to retire from a formal employment, either by reason of age or length of service in a normal circumstance. Retirement can come as a result of unforeseen vicissitudes of life in the form of involuntary retirement which can arise from a myriad of reasons such as ill-health, disciplinary action, change in the organizational policy

of the institution concerned, or redundancy occasioned by economic down turn in the fortune of the organization, amongst many other reasons (Dansan, 2002). Scholars have identified the causes and sources of pre - retirement anxiety to be associated with poor health, old age, financial insecurity, loss of job roles, dissatisfaction and loss of social support and self - esteem among others, as the factors accompanying retirement transition. Moreover, the challenges of retirees range from inadequate income, delay in the payment of retirement entitlements, poor health medication, lack of personal accommodation, inadequate investment and poor savings, difficulties in getting post - retirement vocational substitute, society's negative perception to retirees and reduced social networking (Olatomide in Baba, Garba and Zakariyah, 2015).

Anxiety is one of the most emotional responses that a person can experience. It is a condition in which a person is concerned about the likelihood of a negative occurrence occurring. This sensation might range in intensity from mild to severe terror (Molin, et al 2021, p.234). Physiological signs associated with anxiety include elevated blood pressure, muscle tension, excessive thirst, and perspiration of the hands and feet. This sort of anxiety, which is typically triggered by risky situations, produces an emotion that is unique to each person and is only temporary linked to a specific situation. An expression of anxiety may take many forms, including violence, self - harm, and more commonly, physical and verbal aggression. Anxiety has always been recognized as a natural emotion of human being, however, inappropriate expression of anger has negative consequences such as destructive effects on the living quality of the family, interpersonal behavior and mental states of the individuals. Experiencing anxiety is strongly influenced by learning and will very fast shift from one teacher to another. In fact, students whose teachers most of the time remain angry would get irritated easily.

Teachers may transfer aggression to students when they have anxiety in them as regards such all important issue as retirement (Ahmetovic, Becirovic and Dubravac, 2020; Kyriacou and Sutcliffe, 2008). Added to that, anxiety is as a response to negative effect such as anger or depression usually accompanied by potentially pathogenic, physiological and biochemical changes resulting from the aspects of the teacher's job and mediated by the perception that the demands made upon the teacher constituted a threat to his or her self-esteem or well-being and by coping mechanisms activated to reduce the perceived threat (Mufford et al., 2021). Teachers normally get late at school or dodge when they have anxiety. This is in line with Kyriacou (2011) who asserts that teachers who have experienced anxiety, usually dodges classes, have anxiety related diseases, develop fatigue and depression, making them to dodge classes, have less time to handle both curriculum and co-curriculum activities.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to assess pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria follows:

1. Assess the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria.
2. Examine the causes of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria.
3. Investigate if there is relationship between pre - retirement anxiety and job performance among academic staff in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions was raised to guide this study.

1. What are the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?
2. What are the causes of pre - retirement anxiety on Job Performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?
3. Is there any relationship between pre - retirement anxiety and job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

Methodology

The design adopted for this study was descriptive survey research and with all academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria as its population. There are four hundred and eighty (480) male and female academic staff of these colleges spread across twelve (12) institutions. A sample size of two hundred and fourteen (214) academic staff was selected at random using multi-stage sampling technique. Academic staff questionnaire (ACSQ) was used as instrument for data collection in this study. The use of research assistants was appointed, trained and employed in the distribution and retrieval of questionnaire from the respondents (academic staff). Pilot study was conducted in Federal College of Education, Zaria with the administration of twenty (20) copies of questionnaire to the affected staff. Instrument was vetted and subjected to test - retest reliability method

with reliability co-efficient of 0.89 was obtained. Permission was sought using a letter of introduction to all concerned institutions to get their staff on board this investigation. Data analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics on the three (3) formulated research questions for this study.

Results

Research Question 1:

What are the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

Table 1: Respondents opinion on the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff in Federal Colleges of Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD
1	Lateness to work.	47	25	66	76	2.200	1.147
2	Shoddy execution of work assigned to do.	72	39	73	30	2.715	1.078
3	Lack of focus and therefore poor results.	87	26	64	37	2.761	1.160
4	Excessive thinking which may lead to health issues.	102	36	45	31	2.676	1.127
5	Planning to work more hours to get more money, reduction in social life style and inability to meet up with time.	67	50	52	45	2.649	1.131
Cumulative Mean						2.600	

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Decision Mean = 2.500

In table 1 above, it became evident that pre - retirement anxiety has a strong effect on job performance of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. This is because their overall mean agreement level of 2.600 is above the 2.500 decision mean. Specifically, most of the respondents asserted that with pre - retirement anxiety there is lack of focus and therefore poor results by academic staff. The view expressed here attracted the highest mean of 2.761 as a total of 87 respondents indicated strongly agreed, 26 others agreed as against 64 that disagreed and the rest of 37 strongly disagreed. Also, the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria is shoddy execution of work assigned to do. This view attracted the second highest mean of 2.715 as a total of 72 indicated strongly agreed, 39 as agreed as against 73 that disagreed and the rest of 30 strongly disagreed.

Research Question 2:

What are the causes of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

Table 2: Respondents' opinion on causes of pre - retirement anxiety on Job Performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD
1	Fear of regular income as wages or allowances.	109	27	56	22	3.042	1.088
2	Movement restricted to the house, places of worship and market.	44	22	69	79	2.144	1.131
3	Inability to adjust to new social status in the society.	116	27	50	21	3.121	1.075
4	Failure to invest their meagre salaries on children, accommodation and other essential things.	57	28	81	48	2.439	
5	Extravagant life style and high social status above their contemporaries in the society.	69	49	59	37	2.700	1.098
Cumulative Mean						2.689	

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Decision Mean = 2.500

Information from table 2 revealed that the causes of pre - retirement anxiety as it affects job performance of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria are varied. This was evident as their cumulative mean agreement level of 2.689 is higher than the 2.50 decision mean. Specifically, most of the respondents believed that the main causes of anxiety in pre - retirement of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria is fear of regular income as wages or allowances. This view attracted the highest mean response of 3.042 as a total of 109 indicated strongly agreed, while 27 agreed as against 56

that disagreed and the rest of 22 strongly disagreed with this view. Also, respondents expressed opinion of their inability to adjust to new social status in the society, is a cause of their anxiety. This viewpoint had the second highest mean of 3.121 as a total of 116 strongly agreed while 22 agreed as against 50 that disagreed and the rest of 21 who strongly disagreed.

Research Question 3:

Is there any relationship between pre - retirement anxiety and job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

Table 3: Respondents’ opinion on relationship between pre - retirement anxiety and job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD
1	Cordial relations exist between the duo concepts.	70	47	52	45	2.663	1.141
2	Level of anxiety in academic staff determines the efforts they put into the work.	86	34	69	25	2.845	1.083
3	Anxiety can set into the life of any academic staff at anytime especially when there is a target attached to a work being done.	47	26	67	74	2.215	1.142
4	Anxiety is everyday affairs as soon as a staff realizes retirement is drawing closer by the day.	72	39	73	30	2.715	1.078
5	Social and economic life which a staff has enjoyed or still enjoying can be the source of anxiety which affects the job performance leading to his/her retirement.	104	23	54	33	2.925	1.164
Cumulative Mean						2.672	

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Decision Mean = 2.500

There is strong relationship between anxiety in pre - retirement and job performance of academic staff in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Their cumulative mean response of 2.672 is above the 2.500 decision mean. Specifically. Majority of the study respondents opined that the social and economic life which a staff enjoyed or still enjoying can be the source of anxiety which affects the job performance leading to his/her retirement. This viewpoint attracted the highest mean response agreement of 2.925 as a total of 104 strongly agreed while 23 agreed as against 54 that disagreed and the rest of 33 in favour of strongly disagreed. Also, majority of the respondents agreed to the fact that anxiety can set into the life of any academic staff at anytime especially when there is a target attached to a work being done. The opinion expressed here attracted the second highest mean of 2.845 with a total of 86 strongly agreed, 34 agreed as against 69 that disagreed and the rest of 25 who strongly disagreed.

Discussions of Findings

This study assessed pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Three (3) research questions were formulated to guide the study which has been subjected to descriptive statistics. Research question one tested the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. The outcome of responses from the respondents indicated that pre - retirement anxiety has a strong effect on job performance of academic staff of these Colleges. This was confirmed by Adisa (2003) who stated that income, status, responsibilities, activities and social relationship associated with the work environment suddenly change due to what may be referred to as pre-retirement anxiety of the would-be retired officer.

Research question two tested the causes of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Diverse causes of pre - retirement anxiety was identified in this work. However, the major cause of anxiety prior to retirement is the issue of absence of regular income and reduction in social status among others which may begin to have untold effect on job performance of academic staff of these Colleges. In support of this, Kyriacou (2011) asserted that teachers who have experienced anxiety, usually dodges classes, have anxiety related diseases, develop fatigue and depression, making them to dodge classes, have less time to handle both curriculum and co-curriculum activities. Research question three assessed the relationship between pre - retirement anxiety and job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. It became evident that strong relationship exists between the duo variables. Anxiety is a strong factor that can affect result of work done in an educational institutions in a positive or negative form. In the case of this study, the main interest is on the negative angle to job performance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, pre - retirement anxiety has negative influence on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. There are many causes to this especially with the luxury life lived by academic staff while in service without any tangible preparation for life in retirement. They often get regular income and other allowances and so, they do not foresee retirement coming their ways. Only a little of this number prepared for life in retirement while majority maybe looking older in age and possibly running helter-scamter in need of cash to run their homes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made for this study.

1. Staff due for retirement should be well guided and supported to accept their destiny in good fate but not as something that would make them to lack focus and thus produced poor results in what they are teaching.
2. The government should strengthen and supervise the activities of various Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs) in the Country to allay the fear of staff that their remittances while still working will continue to come regularly even in retirement.
3. There should be well structured social life and other economic activities which retirees would enjoyed after leaving the service so as to feel belong and to cater for their needs in retirement.

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